

Human aortic vasoreactivity in response to various stimuli:

A review

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Abstract

The aorta is primarily known for buffering blood volume, a function referred to as the Windkessel function. This function relies on the aorta's multilayered structure of vascular smooth muscle cells that can potentially cause vasoconstriction or dilation, thereby potentially altering the aortic Windkessel function. Understanding the aorta's active contractility is important, especially since vasodilatory drugs are regularly used in e.g. hypertensive treatment. This review evaluates the vasoreactivity of the human aorta in response to various stimuli. A systematic search of the PubMed database was conducted for articles published before 1 January 2024. Of 1179 articles that were screened for inclusion, 30 articles met the inclusion criteria. Ten studies involved *ex vivo* examinations, while 20 studies involved *in vivo* measurements. *Ex vivo* pharmacological testing revealed vasoconstriction induced by adrenergic and endothelin-A receptor agonists, as well as prostanoids. Conversely, pharmacological vasodilation was observed following administration of nitrates and calcium channel blockers, although acetylcholine did not induce vasodilation *ex vivo*. Additionally, tobacco smoking and intravenous cocaine use were associated with vasoconstriction, whereas anesthetic agents were involved in potential aortic vasodilation. These findings challenge the traditional view of the aorta as a passive conduit, highlighting its vasoreactive properties in response to vasoactive stimuli. This revised understanding has significant implications for prescribing antihypertensive drugs, which commonly have a vasodilatory effect. The potential impact of these therapies on the aorta's Windkessel function warrants careful consideration, particularly in patients with aortic pathologies.

Keywords: Human, Aorta, Vasoreactivity, Vasoconstriction, Vasodilation

Introduction

The aorta, the largest artery in the human body, plays a crucial role in the systemic circulation by distributing blood from the heart to other parts of the body. As an elastic artery, it functions as a buffering chamber, expanding during systole to accommodate the blood ejected from the heart and recoiling during diastole. This process is known as the aorta's Windkessel function (1). Besides containing a significant amount of elastin in its wall (up to 40% in the thoracic aorta (1)), the human aorta also contains multiple layers of vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMCs). These cells synthesize extracellular matrix (ECM) but are potentially also capable of actively modulating aortic diameter through vasoconstriction and -dilation.

Understanding the extent of vasoreactivity in the human aorta is essential, especially since vasodilatory drugs, such as calcium channel blockers, are recommended as part of the initial pharmacological intervention in the treatment guidelines of hypertension (2). Interestingly, vasodilation can potentially increase or decrease functional vascular stiffness, depending on the working pressure and the ECM composition (3, 4). At low pressures in elastic arteries, most load is borne by elastin. When VSMCs contract, they take over this load from the elastic material, typically making the artery stiffer. Conversely, at higher pressures and stiffer arteries, collagen is more engaged. Vasoconstriction would then take load away from this stiff component, resulting in de-stiffening. This is particularly significant in the aorta, where increased arterial stiffness compromises its Windkessel function, leading to increases in pulse pressure and systolic blood pressure. Consequently, these elevated pressures increase the risk of cardiovascular diseases, stroke, dementia, and renal diseases (5).

This review aims to explore the extent to which the human aorta can actively modulate its vascular tone by vasoconstriction or -dilation in response to diverse stimuli. The analysis comprises the impact of diverse stimuli, including vasoactive drugs and hemodynamic triggers of a physical nature. Additionally, the review considers the response of several parameters to vasoactive stimuli as indicators of vasoactive behavior. This includes alterations of *ex vivo* generated force, and *in vivo* aortic diameter or local stiffness parameters.

Methods

Search strategy

We conducted a literature search on articles listed in the PubMed database published before January 1, 2024, to explore human aortic vasoreactivity. The search term utilized a combination of Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms, free keywords, and Boolean operators related to the terms

human, aorta, and vasoreactivity, including *vasoconstriction* or *vasodilation*. To focus on human studies, the search term excluded all articles mentioning animal experiments in their title or abstract, unless they also contained terms resembling *human* in the title. The complete search strategy is provided in **Supplemental Digital Content 1** and underwent secondary review by an independent assessor. PubMed filters were used to exclude review articles and non-English full-text publications. Additionally, we analyzed the reference lists of included articles and of excluded review articles to identify any potentially missed studies.

Inclusion criteria

This review employed four primary inclusion criteria that must hold simultaneously. First, only articles featuring aortic reactivity experiments in human (tissue). Articles reporting vasoreactivity in other arteries, such as brachial flow-mediated dilation experiments, were excluded, as were *in silico* models of the human aorta. Studies investigating the effects of vasoconstriction or -dilation at a cellular or molecular level were also excluded to maintain focus on tissue-level impacts.

Second, only studies directly assessing vasoreactivity, defined as *ex vivo* force generation or *in vivo* acute changes in diameter and/or in local stiffness of the aorta, were included. An acute response is defined to occur within 1 hour. Aortic stiffness should be assessed locally, rather than globally (e.g. through carotid-femoral pulse wave velocity).

Third, only non-reviews, English, and non-retracted articles were included for consideration. All articles were evaluated for eligibility by two independent assessors; disagreements between the assessors were solved in a consensus meeting.

Data extraction

Data from included studies were extracted and collected in a table by the first assessor. This process was subsequently checked by the independent second assessor. From all studies, the following information was extracted: type of participants or donors, number of participants or samples, the investigated aortic segment, and the stimulus for vasoreactivity (including details such as type, duration and/or concentration of the stimulus). From *ex vivo* studies, the following additional information was extracted: size and orientation of the tissue sample, maximally generated force/stress by the stimulus, and the preload used. From *in vivo* studies the following additional information was extracted from before and after the stimulus: pressure and diameter values (diastolic, systolic, mean and pulsatile change) and local stiffness parameters such as distensibility and local pulse wave velocity. Data are noted as mean \pm standard deviation, unless stated otherwise.

Definitions of vasoreactivity

A clear definition of vasoactive response is essential for interpreting the included *in vivo* and *ex vivo* studies investigating aortic reactivity. In *ex vivo* studies, the interpretation is straightforward: increased generated force or stress signifies vasoconstriction, while decreased force indicates vasodilation. The interpretation of *in vivo* studies presents greater complexity due to the interdependence of vessel diameter and stiffness on blood pressure, as illustrated in **Figure 1**.

In vivo vasoconstriction is characterized by decreased diameter concurrent with increased pressure, whereas vasodilation manifests as increased diameter accompanied by decreased pressure (**Figure 1A**). Changes towards the alternative quadrants of **Figure 1A** represent passive mechanical responses: diameter shrinkage from pressure reduction or expansion from pressure elevation. Similarly, arterial stiffness parameters demonstrate pressure dependence, as depicted in **Figure 1B**. Under passive conditions, increased pressure correlates with elevated stiffness and reduced distensibility. Deviations from these expected mechanical responses suggest vasoactive behavior.

Results

Article selection and data extraction

The initial search resulted in 1,428 articles (**Figure 2**). By using PubMed filters, 253 non-English and review articles were excluded. Titles and abstracts of the resulting 1,175 articles were examined for the previously mentioned inclusion criteria. Finally, 30 articles were included in this review, of which 10 articles contained *ex vivo* experiments while the others contained *in vivo* measurements. An overview of the extracted data from the included articles can be found in **Tables 1** and **2**, for *ex vivo* and *in vivo* studies respectively. General physiological information about the different included compounds and stimuli can be found in **Supplemental Digital Content 2**.

Structure of results

First, studies using pharmacologically induced vasoconstriction will be discussed, followed by studies using pharmacologically induced vasodilation. Then, non-pharmacological vasoactive stimuli will be addressed, including exercise, sympathetic activation through cold pressor test, lower body negative pressure, and head-up tilting, as well as substance exposure from tobacco smoking, intravenous cocaine usage, and anesthetic administration. Finally, *ex vivo* studies reporting spontaneous contractility will be discussed.

Pharmacologically induced vasoconstriction

Potassium depolarization

Direct membrane depolarization, as induced *ex vivo* by an increased potassium concentration in five included studies, results in force generation (indicating possible vasoconstriction) in human aortic tissue. These five studies used elevated potassium concentrations ranging from 50 to 127 mM to investigate its vasoactive effect on aortic tissue from organ donors (6, 7), juxta ductal coarctated aorta patients (8), ischemic heart disease patients undergoing transplantation (9), and a patient with Klippel-Trenaunay syndrome (10). Klippel-Trenaunay syndrome is a complex genetic syndrome associated with hypertrophy of the lower limbs causing vascular abnormalities (11).

The aortic tissue in these studies showed total force generations between 1.0 and 1.5 g (6, 7, 9), while normalized measurements yielded 55.8 to 135.8 mN per gram tissue (8). Additionally, average total stress generations of 6.37 and 11.5 kPa in circumferential and longitudinal directions respectively were reported (10). These vasoactive responses were not affected by age (7), but were significantly lower in prestenotic sections from the juxta ductal coarctated aorta compared to poststenotic sections (8). Decontamination of tissue samples using an antibiotic mixture significantly reduced the vasoactive response, while cryopreservation almost eliminated this response (6).

Adrenoreceptor stimulation

Adrenergic receptor stimulation was found to result in vasoconstrictive behavior in human aortic tissue *ex vivo* (6-8, 10, 12-14), where stimulation of the α_{1A} -receptor is the primary pathway (12). The vasoactive response was investigated in aortic tissue from patients operated on abdominal aortic aneurysm (12) or a coarctated aorta (8), healthy organ donors (7, 13, 14) and one organ donor with Klippel-Trenaunay syndrome (10).

Non-selective adrenergic stimulation with noradrenaline (18 μ M to 1 mM) (7, 8, 13) and adrenaline (1 mM) (12) resulted in significant force generation, comparable to (8) or exceeding (7) that induced by direct (potassium-induced) membrane depolarization. Addition of noradrenaline (18 μ M) on top of an already increased potassium concentration (60 mM) also showed significant additional force generation (10, 14). Selective stimulation of the α_1 adrenergic receptor by phenylephrine (PE) (0.1 to 1 mM) also resulted in significant force generation in aortic strips from organ donors (6) and abdominal aortic aneurysm patients (12). Gnus et al. (12) used different selective antagonists to show that the α_{1A} -receptor is most important in this response.

The vasoactive response to adrenergic stimulation was shown to be positively correlated with age (7), and was again significantly lower in prestenotic sections from the juxta ductal coarctated aorta compared to poststenotic sections (8). Moreover, the generated force was significantly lower in longitudinal strips than in circumferential strips (14), although this was not shown in the donor with

Klippel-Trenaunay syndrome (10). Furthermore, adrenergic vasoreactivity was unaffected by decontamination (6), but significantly reduced by cryopreservation (6, 13).

Endothelin receptor stimulation

Stimulation of the endothelin-A (ET_A) receptor induced *ex vivo* force generation in aortic tissue from patients undergoing transplantation for ischemic heart disease (9). The maximal response to partially selective ET_A stimulation by endothelin-1 and sarafotoxin 6b was approximately 40% lower than that from direct membrane depolarization by 50 mM KCl, although sarafotoxin was 2-3 times less potent than endothelin-1. The response to ET-1 was antagonized by a selective ET_A antagonist (BQ123, 3 μM), further indicating the prominent role of ET_A-receptor in aortic vasoreactivity. Attempts to selectively stimulate the endothelin-B (ET_B) receptor by endothelin-3, sarafotoxin 6c (S6c), BQ3020 and Ala^{1,3,11,15}-ET-1 did not result in vasoactive behavior of these aortic strips (9, 15), indicating absence of ET_B receptors in the human aorta.

Prostanoids

Administration of the prostanoid prostaglandin F-2α (PGF_{2α}) resulted in significant force generation (indicating vasoconstriction) in aortic strips from juxtaductal coarctation of the aorta patients in a study from Sehested et al. (8). A concentration of 28 μM PGF_{2α} induced 73.8 to 155.5 mN per gram tissue force generation, which was not significantly different from the response to noradrenaline (concentration of 18 μM) and direct membrane depolarization by elevated potassium concentration (concentration of 127 mM). Again, the vasoconstrictive response was greater in poststenotic sections than in prestenotic sections.

Pharmacologically induced vasodilation

Nitrates

The human aorta shows vasodilatory behavior in response to nitrates, such as nitroglycerin (NTG, organic nitrate) (16-19), sodium nitroprusside (SNP, inorganic nitrate) (6, 7, 13) and isosorbide dinitrate (organic nitrate) (20). In *ex vivo* studies, SNP was added on top of a vasoconstrictor (noradrenaline (6, 7) or phenylephrine (13)) to see its vasodilatory effect on aortic tissue from organ donors. Administration of SNP (10 μM to 10 mM) resulted in significant force decrease (6, 13), which was not affected by age (7) or decontamination using an antibiotic mixture (6), but was significantly reduced by cryopreservation (6, 13).

After nitrate administration *in vivo*, systolic pressure decreased significantly in all studies that measured the pressure (16, 17, 20, 21), while diastolic pressure decreased (16, 20, 21) or remained constant (17, 20). Corresponding diameter measurements revealed either maintenance (19) or

increases (18) in mean diameter, and an increased diastolic diameter (20), indicating vasodilation (**Figure 1A**). Distensibility increased after NTG (16), while pulse wave velocity (PWV) did not change significantly after NTG (17) or increased after SNP (21). These changes in stiffness-like parameters can be mostly attributed to passive changes from the decreasing pressure, although the constant PWV could also suggest vasoactive behavior (**Figure 1B**).

The vasodilatory effect of nitrates was shown not to be affected by age (7, 21) or decontamination by an antibiotic mixture (6), but was significantly reduced by cryopreservation (6, 13). Moreover, the pressure lowering effect of nitrates was more pronounced in hypertensive than in normotensive individuals, while the opposite was true for the diameter elevation (20).

Acetylcholine

Administration of acetylcholine (ACh) did not show significant vasodilation in the human aorta, when administered *ex vivo* in concentrations ranging from of 10 μ M to 10 mM (6, 7, 13) after precontraction with phenylephrine (6, 7) or noradrenaline (13).

Adrenergic beta blockers

Selective adrenergic β_1 inhibition by the beta-blocker metoprolol did not conclusively demonstrate vasodilation in the ascending aorta of healthy control subjects and Marfan patients (22). The systolic and pulse pressure decreased in both groups after metoprolol administration, although the statistical significance of this finding was not reported. In healthy individuals, the distensibility increased after metoprolol, while the stiffness index β decreased. The change in distensibility could passively result from the pressure increase, rather than actively from vasoreactivity (**Figure 1B**). Conversely, given that the stiffness index β is largely pressure-independent (23), the observed decrease suggests vasoactive behavior in response to metoprolol. In Marfan patients, the aortic stiffness in did not significantly change on average after metoprolol administration (22). However, the response was heterogeneous, with one subgroup showing significantly decreasing stiffness index β and increasing distensibility, while another subgroup exhibited significant increased stiffness index β and a trend towards distensibility decrease (22). This heterogeneity seemed to correlate with the disease stage. Patients with smaller aortic dilation showed decreased stiffness, while those with larger aortic dilation showed no significant change or even increased stiffness after metoprolol administration (22). Given again the pressure-independence of stiffness index β (23), the observed changes after metoprolol administration suggest vasoreactivity in both subgroups.

Calcium antagonists

Calcium antagonists induce vasodilatory behavior in the human aorta, as shown for nifedipine (24) and diltiazem (25). *In vivo*, the systolic (24, 25), diastolic (24, 25), mean (24) and pulse (25) pressure decreased in normotensive and hypertensive individuals. In both studies, the systolic diameter increased in normotensive people (24, 25), which indicates vasodilation as shown in **Figure 1A**. Meanwhile the diastolic diameter decreased after diltiazem administration in these normotensive individuals (25), possibly passively originating from the pressure drop. However, the same individuals also showed a rightward shift of the pressure-diameter curve (25), again indicating vasodilation. Furthermore, aortic diameter did not show significant changes in hypertensive individuals (24, 25). Combined with the observed pressure decrease, this also suggests vasodilation, as shown in **Figure 1A**. The pulsatile strain and distensibility increased (24, 25), while the stiffness index decreased (25); all indicating a decreasing aortic stiffness. This could be attributed to the pressure decrease, as illustrated in **Figure 1B**.

Endothelium-derived hyperpolarization factors

The *ex vivo* administration of H₂O₂, an endothelium-derived hyperpolarization factor, demonstrated vasodilatory behavior of human aortic tissue from organ donors (7). After contraction with NA, additional administration of H₂O₂ (concentrations ranging from 1 μM to 1 mM) reduced the generated force. This vasodilatory response was negatively correlated with age, since relaxation was significantly impaired in tissue from donors aged 65 years and older.

Non-pharmacological vasoreactivity

Spontaneous

In *ex vivo* studies, human aortic tissue also demonstrated spontaneous contractility (12, 26). When aortic tissue from abdominal aortic aneurysm patients was placed into an incubation chamber, it spontaneously generated forces with amplitudes of 0.8 mN, lasting approximately 39 seconds per contraction at a frequency of 0.5 contractions per minute (26). This behavior persisted for several hours (26). No statistically significant difference in force generation was observed between longitudinal and circumferential sections (26).

Exercise

Two studies investigating aortic hemodynamics during exercise (27, 28) suggest that the aorta does not actively modulate its vascular tone during exercise. In these studies, participants performed static leg weightlifting (27) and supine bicycling (28). Pressure measurements revealed significant increases during exercise, including diastolic (27, 28), systolic (27, 28), and mean arterial pressure (27), while pulse pressure remained unchanged (27). The aortic diameter increased significantly in

diastole (27), potentially passively caused by the elevated pressure (**Figure 1A**), but showed no change in systole (27). Pulsatile area change either decreased (27) or remained constant (28), resulting in a significant (28) or near-significant (27) reduction in distensibility. The stiffness index showed an almost significant increase (28). These observed changes in stiffness-related indices appear to represent a passive response to the pressure elevation during exercise rather than vasoreactivity (**Figure 1B**).

Cold pressor test

The cold pressor test (CPT) revealed limited sympathetic-induced vascular reactivity of the human aorta across different participant groups (18, 29). During the test, participants submerge one hand in ice-cold water, triggering a sympathetic response of the autonomic nervous system. Although these studies did not report direct pressure measurements, this trigger typically results in an elevated pressure. Abdominal aortic diameter increased after CPT (18, 29), suggesting a passive response to the pressure increase (**Figure 1A**). Notably, this diameter response was significantly attenuated in smokers (18) and absent in patients with abdominal aortic aneurysm (AAA) (29).

Lower body negative pressure

Lower body negative pressure elicited minimal aortic hemodynamic changes, indicating a lack of significant vasoactive response across different age groups (30). The mean aortic pressure remained constant in healthy young and elderly participants, while the diastolic pressure increased significantly (30). Moreover, the mean aortic diameter did not change significantly, nor did the arterial stiffness, measured by Peterson's elastic modulus and stiffness constant β (30).

Non-bleeding fluid deficiency

Scuba diving as a model of non-bleeding fluid deficiency showed no significant aortic hemodynamic changes, although possibly a minimal vasodilatory response after the first dive (31). The increasing external pressure during immersion in water causes blood to shift from the extremities to the central circulation. The baroreceptors activate the parasympathetic nervous system to reduce heart rate and blood pressure during the dive. Moreover, the blood volume is reduced by promoting diuresis with atrial natriuretic peptide (ANP) release. After the dive, the redistribution of blood triggers the sympathetic nervous system to maintain cardiac output and central blood pressure. This complex mechanism was investigated during this study. On average, no significant changes of the aortic blood pressure and diameter were observed (31). However, separate analysis of the first dive showed a constant aortic pressure with a significant increase in diastolic diameter (31), suggesting vasodilation (**Figure 1A**).

Tilting

Baroreflex stimulation by head-up tilt testing did not show any aortic vasoactive behavior in healthy participants, but possibly resulted in vasodilation in patients with severe congestive heart failure (32). In control participants, the aortic pressure and diameter remained constant after head-up tilt (32). Conversely, in patients with congestive heart failure, the aortic mean and systolic pressure decreased significantly after tilting, while the pulse pressure remained constant (32). Meanwhile, the systolic diameter of the aortic root increased significantly, while the decrease in diastolic diameter was nonsignificant, which resulted in an increase in pulsatile stretch (32). This behavior suggests aortic vasodilation in response to head-up tilt only in congestive heart failure patients, as illustrated in **Figure 1A**.

Smoking

Tobacco smoking has several effects on the vasoreactivity of the human aorta. Firstly, the aorta acutely showed signs of vasoconstriction in response to active, but not to passive and sham smoking (33). Active smoking resulted in an acute increase in systolic and diastolic pressure, while the systolic and diastolic diameter did not significantly change (33), which could possibly indicate vasoconstriction as defined in **Figure 1A**. Distensibility and pulsatile diameter changes decreased after active smoking, while the mean slope of the pressure-diameter curve increased (33), all indicating arterial stiffening. These changes in stiffness-like indices are assumed to passively result from the smoking induced blood pressure increase, as shown in **Figure 1B**. Passive smoking led to a significant increase in systolic, diastolic and pulse pressure in nonsmokers, also resulting in an increase of systolic and diastolic diameter (33). Moreover, the pulsatile diameter change and distensibility decreased, while the average slope of the pressure–diameter relation increased, all indicating arterial stiffening (33). These changes in response to passive smoking are assumed to passively result from the increasing pressure, as defined in **Figure 1A-B**. Sham smoking did not lead to any significant changes in pressures, diameter, or stiffness parameters (33).

Secondly, research by Chandraratna et al. (18) indicated that long-term smoking reduces the aortic vasodilatory response to nitroglycerin and the CPT.

Thirdly, the fetal aorta might also respond vasoactively to maternal smoking. During maternal smoking, the diastolic diameter of the fetal aorta increases, while the pulsatile diameter change also increases (34). Unfortunately, fetal pressure was not reported in this study, but the fetal heart rate increased significantly (34). The pressure is therefore assumed to increase during smoking, which could passively explain the increased diastolic diameter (**Figure 1A**). However, this elevated pressure would passively result in a decrease in pulsatile diameter change (**Figure 1B**), rather than the

reported increase (34). Therefore, this fetal response to maternal smoking is possibly the result of active aortic tone modulation.

Cocaine

Intravenous infusion of cocaine acutely results in vasoconstriction of the thoracic aorta, as shown by Eisenberg et al. (35). This is demonstrated by the constant diameter of the ascending and descending aorta, despite the immediate increase in systolic pressure (35).

Anesthetics

Anesthesia with propofol possibly shows aortic vasodilation, while this cannot be distinguished anymore when nitrous oxide added (36). During anesthesia with propofol and air with 30% oxygen, the mean aortic pressure decreases depending on the dosage, while the aortic diameter only significantly decreases at plasma concentration of 3 µg/mL (36). **Figure 1A** indicates that the constant diameter could be attributed to active vasodilation. When air is replaced with N₂O while maintaining 30% oxygen, the mean aortic pressure is significantly more decreased at the highest plasma concentration of 5 µg/ml (36). Here, the diameter decreases significantly at all plasma concentrations (36), as expected passively from the pressure decrease (**Figure 1A**).

Meal consumption

The abdominal aorta did not show any vasoactive effect after meal consumption through duodenal feeding (37). The diastolic and systolic diameter did not significantly change, while the aortic pressure was not measured (37).

Discussion

This review summarizes human aortic vasoreactivity in response to various stimuli. It demonstrated vasodilation and vasoconstriction in response to most pharmacological vasoactive compounds, both *ex vivo* and *in vivo*. The endothelin-A and adrenergic α_1 receptor were identified to play a key role in vasoreactivity of the human aorta. Non-pharmacologically induced vasoconstriction was seen after substance use by tobacco smoking or intravenous cocaine injection. Vasoreactivity could not be recognized in response to other stimuli such as exercise and various procedures designed to activate the sympathetic nervous system.

Demographic and health factors

Most studies showed vasoactive behavior, despite the heterogeneity of participants, donors, and investigated aortic region. The effect of age on the aortic vasoreactivity was investigated by several studies, although in small group sizes ($n=6$ to $n=18$). Contraction by noradrenaline administration *ex*

vivo was positively correlated with age (7, 8). Conversely, when noradrenaline administration was combined with potassium depolarization, the vasoconstrictive response was negatively correlated with age (14). Vasodilation by hydrogen peroxide was also reduced in the oldest age group (7), while no significant differences across age groups were observed after nitrogen peroxide administration (7, 21). Hypertension does not influence the vasodilatory response to nitrates (19, 20) and calcium channel blockers (24, 25), but long-term smoking does impair the response to nitroglycerin (18).

Implications

This review emphasizes that not only the arterioles and peripheral arteries dilate in response to vasodilatory antihypertensive drugs, but also the aorta. These findings underscore the active role of the human aorta in hemodynamics, alongside its well-recognized passive buffering function. We recommend that this notion is incorporated in educational textbooks and considered when investigating aortic biomechanics.

Acknowledging this aortic vasoreactivity is also important for clinical decision making. As mentioned before, research has shown that vasodilation affects arterial stiffness. Depending on the pressure and extracellular matrix composition, such vasodilation can cause stiffening or de-stiffening (3). Arterial stiffening of the aorta compromises its Windkessel function. This increases the load on the heart and the pulse pressure downstream, which could cause end-organ damage. Therefore, these effects of aortic vasoreactivity should be considered when prescribing vasodilatory drugs.

The presence of an aortic aneurysm adds another layer of complexity when prescribing vasodilatory drugs. In aneurysm patients, treatment focuses on slowing down the widening of the aorta and reducing the risk of dissection or rupture. Vasodilatory drugs seem to be potentially helpful by reducing the blood pressure, which decreases the stress on the vascular wall. However, according to the Laplace law ($\sigma_{\theta} = (P \cdot d)/(2h)$), wall stress (σ_{θ}) depends not only on blood pressure (P), but also increases linearly with arterial diameter (d). As vasodilation occurs, the arterial wall thickness (h) decreases due to mass conservation, which further increases wall stress. Therefore, while these drugs may lower blood pressure, their vasodilatory effects on the aorta could counteract the potential benefits on wall stress.

Data synthesis

This review also shows that there is no standardized method yet to quantify vasoreactivity, especially in the human aorta. Not only was there large heterogeneity in the vasoactive stimuli, but the reported outcome parameters also varied significantly. On the one hand, *ex vivo* studies reported generated force in different quantities (e.g. absolute force, stress (per gram tissue) or percentile force generation compared to potassium depolarization), complicating the integration

and comparison of the results of different studies. Moreover, these studies did not report how this force generation would relate to an *in vivo* situation. On the other hand, *in vivo* studies reported data inconsistently, for example by lacking crucial information on blood pressure. Therefore, the quantification of human aortic vasoreactivity, and its local effect on arterial stiffness, is to be investigated further.

Limitations

The large variability in how results were reported in the different studies required simplification of our data analysis. The findings of *ex vivo* studies were summarized based on the presence or absence of vasoreactivity, rather than quantifying this response. Moreover, the results of *in vivo* studies were simplified to either significant or non-significant changes of pressure, diameter and stiffness values. To distinguish vasoactive behavior from the passive pressure dependency of diameter and stiffness, vasoreactivity was only recognized as such when certain criteria were met (**Figure 1**). This limited our analysis, especially when considering *in vivo* non-pharmacological stimuli. Dedicated studies on the aortic response to specific stimuli are recommended to better aortic vasoreactivity.

Although the outcome of the *ex vivo* studies appear less complicated to interpret, the statistical significance of these findings was often not reported. This raises concerns about the reliability of the reported results, especially in studies where sample size was low.

This review intends to answer the question on whether the human aorta is capable of vasoactive behavior. Data from all regions of the aorta were combined, without accounting for regional differences. However, when further quantifying this response in future research, differences in wall composition across the aorta should be considered.

Conclusions

This review underscores the dynamic role of the human aorta, which demonstrates active contractile and dilatory functions in addition to its well-established passive buffering capacity. *Ex vivo* studies reveal different receptors and pathways contributing to the active behavior of the aorta, including the adrenergic α_1 receptor, the ET_A receptor and nitric oxide-mediated vasodilation. Complementary *in vivo* studies confirm the effect of different pharmacological stimuli and explore the effect of other physiological stimuli. Acknowledging the possible effects of aortic vasoreactivity is important when prescribing vasodilatory antihypertensive drugs, especially in aneurysm patients.

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Figure 1: Interpretation of vasoconstriction and vasodilation from *in vivo* studies. **A:** Passively, the diameter increases with increasing pressure and vice versa. Vasoconstriction is then defined when the diameter remains unchanged or decreases despite increasing pressure, while vasodilation is when the diameter remains unchanged or increases as pressure decreases. **B:** Passively, the stiffness increases at higher pressures, while the distensibility decreases, as illustrated by the slope of the pressure-diameter curve. When *in vivo* studies report a contrasting response of the aorta to a stimulus, deviating from its passive mechanical behavior, this is defined as vasoactive behavior.

Figure 2: Inclusion flowchart. *n* denotes the number of included articles at that stage.

Table 1: Overview of *ex vivo* studies on aortic vasoreactivity

First author	Year	Ref	Donors	Aortic segment	Compound / Stimulus	Effect	Additional findings
Amabili	2023	(10)	Female donor with Klippel-Trenaunay syndrome ($n=1$).	Descending aorta	KCl NA	C C	Leftward shift of stress-strain curve from baseline to contracted. More stress generation longitudinal than circumferential.
Assar	2022	(7)	Deceased organ donors. Age groups <40 ($n=10$), 40-55 ($n=18$), 55-65 ($n=11$) and >65 ($n=12$) years.	-	KCl NA ACh SNP H ₂ O ₂	C C No ? D	KCl and SNP response not affected by age. ACh response inexistent. NA response positively correlated with age ($r^2=0.179$, $p=0.0052$). H ₂ O ₂ response negatively correlated with age ($r^2 = 0.17$, $p=0.0066$).
Davenport	1993	(15)	Patients undergoing transplantation	-	ET _B stimulation	No	
Franchini	2022	(14)	Heart-beating donors ($n=13$). Age groups 25-48 ($n=7$) and 55-68 ($n=6$) years.	Descending aorta	KCl + NA	C	Active stress-strain curve shifted to leftward, and significantly less curved (more linear) than baseline. Significantly less activating stress in older age group than the younger group only in longitudinal direction, not circumferential ($p=0.0391$, $p=0.7274$).
Gnus	2012	(26)	Aneurysm patients for elective repair surgery ($n=18$).	Abdominal aortic aneurysm	Spontaneous	C	No statistical difference in longitudinal and circumferential sections.
Gnus	2012	(12)	Aneurysm patients for elective repair surgery ($n=10$).	Abdominal aortic aneurysm	Spontaneous Adrenergic stimulation Adrenergic inhibition	? C D	Stimulation and blockage of different adrenergic subtypes shows a role for the α_1 -adrenergic receptor. Key role for α_{1A} suggested, less pronounced effect of α_{1B} and α_{1D} receptors
Langerak	2001	(6)	Non-beating heart valve donors without known aortic disease ($n=14$).	Descending aorta	KCl PE ACh SNP	C C No D	Acetylcholine response inexistent. Only KCl response is significantly reduced after decontamination ($p=0.02$). All vasoreactivity significantly reduced after cryopreservation
Maguire	1995	(9)	From recipient hearts of patients undergoing transplantation for ischemic heart disease ($n=4$)	-	Spontaneous KCl ET _A stimulation ET _A inhibition ET _B stimulation ET _B inhibition	? C C D No No	Sometimes spontaneous rhythmic contractions observed, mostly in other arteries.
Rendal Vazquez	2004	(13)	Organ donors ($n=7$)	Thoracic descending aorta	NA ACh SNP	C No D	Acetylcholine response inexistent. NA and SNP response significantly affected by cryopreservation ($p<0.05$)

First author	Year	Ref	Donors	Aortic segment	Compound / Stimulus	Effect	Additional findings
Sehested	1982	(8)	Patients with juxtaductal coarctated aorta ($n=8$)	Sections prestenotic, stenotic and poststenotic	KCl NA PGF _{2α}	C C C	Response to KCl, NA and PGF _{2α} administration significantly higher poststenotic ($p<0.005$, $p<0.05$, $p<0.05$) than prestenotic. In the prestenotic segments, mean contractile response negatively correlated with intra-arterial systolic pressure in brachial artery. No age correlation found.

The included articles don't report the significance of the reported vasoactive behavior. Effect is summarized as: C, vasocontractile response is present; D, vasodilative response is present; No, no vasoactive response to this stimulus; and ?, the vasoactive response was not further discussed in the article. Abbreviations: KCl, increased potassium chloride concentration; NA, noradrenalin; ACh, acetylcholine; SNP, sodium nitroprusside; H₂O₂, hydrogen peroxide; ET, endothelin; PE, phenylephrine; PGF_{2α}, prostaglandin F-2α.

Table 2: Overview of *in vivo* studies regarding aortic vasoreactivity

First author	Year	Ref	Aortic segment	Patients / Participants	Compound / Stimulus	Effect	Pressure	Diameter	Stiffness	Additional findings
Alegret	2015	(27)	Ascending aorta	Healthy volunteers (n=12)	Exercise	?	Dia: ↑ (p=0.025) Sys: ↑ (p<0.001) Mean: ↑ (p= 0.001) Δ: N.S.	Dia: ↑ (p = 0.031) Sys: N.S. Δ: ↑ (p= 0.014)	Dist: N.S.	
Carroll	1991	(21)	Thoracic aorta	Patients with dilated cardiomyopathy (n=25)	SNP	?	Dia: ↓ (p<0.001) Sys: ↓ (p<0.001)		PWV: ↓ (p<0.01)	Systolic pressure amplification decreased after SNP (p<0.001). Age effect in PWV change: for a given change in distending pressure the oldest group had a greater change in pulse wave velocity (p<0.01).
Chandraratna	2009	(18)	Abdominal aorta	Controls (n=33)	CPT	?		Mean: ↑		Significance of responses not given in the article. Smokers significant less vasodilation in response to CPT and NTG (p<0.002).
					NTG	D		Mean: ↑		
					CPT	?		Mean: ↑		
					NTG	D		Mean: ↑		
Chen	2014	(28)	Proximal ascending aorta	Controls (n=22)	Exercise	?	Dia: ↑ (p<0.001) Sys: ↑ (p<0.001)	Δ: N.S.	Dist: ↓ (p<0.001) SI: N.S.	Patients had significantly higher systolic pressure during rest and exercise than controls. Patients had significantly lower aortic strain, distensibility, and greater stiffness index during rest and exercise than controls. Patients had less change in distensibility after exercise than controls.
						Patients (n=30)	?	Dia: ↑ (p<0.001) Sys: ↑ (p<0.001)	Δ: N.S.	
Collette	2011	(16)	Thoracic aorta	Patients 18-88 years old (n=52)	NTG	?	Dia: ↓ (p<0.001) Sys: ↓ (p<0.001) Mean: ↓ (p<0.01)		Dist: ↑ (p<0.001) SI: N.S.	
Eisenberg	1996	(35)	Ascending and descending at 2 levels	IV cocaine using volunteers, 20-45 years (n=15)	IV Cocaine	?	Sys: ↑ (p<0.01)	Mean: N.S.		Diameter change was not significantly different at all three aortic locations.

First author	Year	Ref	Aortic segment	Patients / Participants	Compound / Stimulus	Effect	Pressure	Diameter	Stiffness	Additional findings
Fichtner	2021	(31)	Thoracic aorta	Experienced divers (n=41)		All dives	No	Dia: N.S. Sys: N.S.	Dia: N.S. Sys: N.S.	
						First dive	No	Dia: N.S. Sys: N.S.	Dia: ↑ (p=0.034) Sys: N.S.	
						Repetition dives	No	Dia: N.S. Sys: N.S.	Dia: N.S. Sys: N.S.	
Geelkerken	1998	(37)	Proximal abdominal aorta	Patients undergoing elective abdominal vascular reconstructive surgery (n=14)	Meal stimulation	No		Mean: N.S.		
Haouzi	1997	(22)	Ascending aorta	Controls (n=10)	Metoprolol	?	Dia: N.S. Sys: ? Δ: ?		β: ↓ (p<0.001) Dist: ↑ (p<0.01)	Significance of pressure response not given. Heterogeneous response Marfan patients: increasing and decreasing stiffness index, which was not age related. Stiffness increasing patients tended to have a more dilated aorta than patients where the stiffness decreased.
				Marfan (n=13)		?	Dia: N.S. Sys: ? Δ: ?	β: N.S. Dist: N.S.		
Kassis	1987	(32)	Aortic root	Controls (n=7)	45° Tilting	No	Sys: N.S. Mean: N.S. Δ: N.S.	Dia: N.S. Sys: N.S. Δ: N.S.		
				Congestive heart failure patients (n=7)		D	Sys: ↓ (p<0.02) Mean: ↓ (p<0.02) Δ: N.S.	Dia: N.S. Sys: ↑ (p<0.02) Δ: ↑ (p<0.02)		
Pannier	1990	(20)	Aortic arch	Normotensives (n=9)	Isosorbide dinitrate	D	Sys: ↓ (p<0.05) Mean: N.S. Δ: ↓ (p<0.01)	Dia: ↑ (p<0.001)		
				Hypertensives (n=12)		D	Sys: ↓ (p<0.001) Mean: ↓ (p<0.001) Δ: ↓ (p<0.05)	Dia: ↑ (p<0.05)		

First author	Year	Ref	Aortic segment	Patients / Participants	Compound / Stimulus	Pressure	Diameter	Stiffness	Additional findings	
Sakurai	2007	(17)	Thoracic aorta	Coronary artery disease / hypertensive heart (<i>n</i> =41)	NTG	?	Dia: N.S. Sys: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.01)	PWV: N.S.	PWV was positively correlated with age and systolic pressure (<i>p</i> <0.001, <i>p</i> <0.001)	
Shiga	2003	(36)	-	Unpremedicated patients for elective surgery (<i>n</i> =30)	Propofol + air (30% oxygen)	?	Mean: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.05)	Mean: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.05)	Diameter decrease in propofol with air treated group only significant at a concentration of 3 µg/ml, not at higher concentrations. Aortic pressure decreases significantly more in patients anesthetized by propofol with 70% N ₂ O at a concentration of 5 µg/ml (<i>p</i> =0.045).	
					Propofol + 70% N ₂ O (30% oxygen)	?	Mean: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.05)	Mean: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.05)		
Sindberg Eriksen	1984	(34)	Fetal descending aorta	Smoking pregnant women and fetus (<i>n</i> =17)	Smoking	?		Dia: ↑ (<i>p</i> <0.01) Δ: ↑ (<i>p</i> <0.01)		
Sonesson	1997	(30)	Abdominal aorta	Young (<i>n</i> =10)	LBNP	?	Dia: ↑ (<i>p</i> <0.01) Sys: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.01) Mean: N.S.	Mean: N.S.	E _p : N.S. β: N.S.	
				Elderly (<i>n</i> =9)		?	Dia: ↑ (<i>p</i> <0.02) Sys: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.05) Mean: N.S.	Mean: N.S.	E _p : N.S. β: N.S.	
Stefanadis	1997	(25)	Descending aorta	Normotensives (<i>n</i> =15)	Diltiazem	D	Dia: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.001) Sys: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.001) Δ: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.005)	Dia: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.05) Sys: ↑ (<i>p</i> <0.001) Δ: ↑ (<i>p</i> <0.001)	Dist: ↑ (<i>p</i> <0.005) SI: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.005)	Slope of stress-strain curve decreased after diltiazem in both groups (<i>p</i> <0.001, <i>p</i> <0.001)
				Hypertensives (<i>n</i> =15)		D	Dia: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.001) Sys: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.001) Δ: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.001)	Dia: N.S. Sys: N.S. Δ: ↑ (<i>p</i> <0.001)	Dist: ↑ (<i>p</i> <0.001) SI: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.001)	
Stefanadis	1998	(33)	Descending aorta	Nonsmokers (<i>n</i> =16)	Passive smoking	?	Dia: ↑ (<i>p</i> <0.001) Sys: ↑ (<i>p</i> <0.001) Δ: ↑ (<i>p</i> =0.005)	Dia: ↑ (<i>p</i> =0.001) Sys: ↑ (<i>p</i> =0.04) Δ: ↓ (<i>p</i> =0.002)	Dist: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.001)	Slope of stress-strain curve increased after passive and active smoking (<i>p</i> <0.001, <i>p</i> <0.001)
				Current smokers (<i>n</i> =32)	Active smoking	?	Dia: ↑ (<i>p</i> <0.001) Sys: ↑ (<i>p</i> =0.001) Δ: N.S.	Dia: N.S. Sys: N.S. Δ: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.001)	Dist: ↓ (<i>p</i> <0.001)	
					Sham smoking	No	Dia: N.S. Sys: N.S. Δ: N.S.	Dia: N.S. Sys: N.S. Δ: N.S.	Dist: N.S.	

First author	Year	Ref	Aortic segment	Patients / Participants	Compound / Stimulus	Effect	Pressure	Diameter	Stiffness	Additional findings
Stratos	1992	(24)	Ascending aorta	Normotensives (n=12)	Nifedipine	D	Dia: ↓ (p<0.01) Sys: ↓ (p<0.001) Mean: ↓ (p<0.005) Δ: N.S.	Dia: N.S. Sys: ↑ (p<0.005) Δ: ↑ (p<0.001)	Dist: ↑ (p<0.001)	More decrease in pressure (dia, sys, mean, and Δ) in hypertensive group than in normotensive group (p<0.001, p<0.005, p<0.001, p<0.05). More increase in sys and Δ diameter in normotensive group than in hypertensive group (p<0.001, p<0.001). More increase in distensibility in normotensive group than in hypertensive group (p<0.001).
				Hypertensives (n=22)		D	Dia: ↓ (p<0.001) Sys: ↓ (p<0.001) Mean: ↓ (p<0.001) Δ: ↓ (p<0.001)	Dia: N.S. Sys: N.S. Δ: ↑ (p<0.001)	Dist: ↑ (p<0.001)	
Strohlm	1983	(19)	Abdominal aorta	Healthy controls (n=14)	NTG	No		Mean: N.S.		
				Healthy research group (n=28)	-	No		Mean: N.S.		
Vermeulen	2022	(29)	Abdominal aorta	Young (n=20)		No		Mean: N.S.		
				Healthy control (n=20)	CPT	No		Mean: N.S.		
				AAA patients (n=15)		No		Mean: N.S.		

The total vasoactive effect is summarized as: C, vasocontractile response is present; D, vasodilative response is present; No, no vasoactive response to this stimulus; and ?, the vasoactive response was not unambiguous (as illustrated in **Figure 1**) or not further discussed in the article. The distinct response of pressure, diameter and arterial stiffness to a stimulus is summarized as: ↑, significantly increasing; ↓, significantly decreasing; N.S., no significant response. Abbreviations: *n*, number of participants; Dia, diastolic; Sys, systolic; Δ, pulsatile difference; Dist, distensibility; PWV, pulse wave velocity; SI, stiffness index; E_p, Peterson's modulus; β, β stiffness constant; IV, intravenous; AAA, abdominal aortic aneurysm; NTG, nitroglycerin; CPT, cold pressor test; LBNP, lower body negative pressure; SNP, sodium nitroprusside.

Supplemental Digital Content 1

PubMed search term

(((((Human*[Title]) OR (Patient*[Title])) OR (((Human[MeSH Terms]) OR (Human*[Title/Abstract]) OR (Patient*[Title/Abstract]) OR (Men[Title/Abstract]) OR (Women [Title/Abstract]))))

NOT (((Rat[Title/Abstract]) OR (Rats[Title/Abstract]) OR (Mice[Title/Abstract]) OR (Mouse[Title/Abstract]) OR (Sheep[Title/Abstract]) OR (Rabbit*[Title/Abstract]) OR (Pig[Title/Abstract]) OR (Pigs[Title/Abstract]) OR (Dog[Title/Abstract]) OR (Dogs[Title/Abstract]) OR (Zebrafish[Title/Abstract]) OR (Ovine[Title/Abstract]) OR (Murine[Title/Abstract]) OR (Porcine[Title/Abstract]) OR (Bovine[Title/Abstract]) OR (Swine[Title/Abstract]) OR (Lamb[Title/Abstract]) OR (Hamster*[Title/Abstract]) OR (Piglet*[Title/Abstract]) OR (Monkey*[Title/Abstract]) OR (Canine[Title/Abstract]) OR (Ferret*[Title/Abstract]) OR (Fish[Title/Abstract]) OR (Cat[Title/Abstract]))))

AND ((Aorta[MeSH Terms]) OR (Aorta[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Aortic arch"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Aortic aneurysm"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Aortic diameter"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Aortic tissue"[Title/Abstract])))

AND ((Vasoconstriction[MeSH Terms]) OR (Vasodilation[MeSH Terms]) OR (Vasoconstriction[Title/Abstract]) OR (Vasodilation[Title/Abstract]) OR (Vasodilatation[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Vascular ton*" [Title/Abstract]) OR ("SMC contraction"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Smooth muscle contraction"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("VSMC contraction"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("VSM contraction"[Title/Abstract]) OR (Contractility[Title/Abstract]) OR ("SMC Activation"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Smooth muscle activation"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("VSMC activation"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("VSM activation"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("SMC relaxation"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Smooth muscle relaxation"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("VSMC relaxation"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("VSM relaxation"[Title/Abstract]) OR (Vasodilator[Title/Abstract]) OR (Vasoreactivity[Title/Abstract]) OR (Vasoconstrictor[Title/Abstract])))

AND ((English[Language])

NOT (Review[Publication Type]))

AND (("1800/08/01"[Date - Publication] : "2024/01/01"[Date - Publication]))

Supplemental Digital Content 2

Potassium depolarization

Direct depolarization of the vascular smooth muscle cells can be experimentally achieved by increasing the potassium concentration of the buffer solution in *ex vivo* experiments. This method is often used to test tissue viability and as comparator for other vasoconstrictive responses.

Adrenoreceptor stimulation or inhibition

In the sympathetic autonomous nervous system, all postganglionic fibers use the neurotransmitter noradrenaline, which acts on the α or β adrenoreceptors (38). These are G protein coupled receptors (GPCRs). There are two α -receptors (α_1 and α_2) each comprising three further subclasses (α_{1A} , α_{1B} , α_{1D} and α_{2A} , α_{2B} , α_{2C}), and three β -receptors subtypes (β_1 , β_2 , and β_3). The α_1 subtypes are most important in the cardiovascular system and urinary tract (38), where stimulation leads to an increased concentration of intracellular calcium ions (12). Conversely, α_2 receptors are mainly neuronal (38). The β_1 receptors are mainly found in the heart, while the β_2 receptors are responsible for smooth muscle relaxation in many organs (38).

The adrenergic agonists used in the studies reviewed herein range from non-selective to increasingly selective agonists targeting these receptors. First, noradrenaline (NA, or norepinephrine) is a non-selective adrenergic receptor agonist with a slight preference for the α -adrenergic receptors (38). In the adrenal medulla, noradrenaline is converted to adrenaline (or epinephrine) which acts as a non-selective agonist, activating all adrenergic receptor subtypes (38). Second, phenylephrine (PE) is an α_1 selective adrenergic agonist (38).

The adrenergic inhibitors used in the included papers are: phentolamine (α - adrenergic antagonist), prazosine (α_1 -adrenergic antagonist), 5-methylurapidil (α_{1A} -adrenergic antagonist), cyclazosine (α_{1B} -adrenergic antagonist), L765314 (α_{1B} -adrenergic antagonist) and BMY 7378 (α_{1D} -adrenergic antagonist) (38), and metoprolol (a β_1 -selective antagonist, also called a beta blocker (38)).

Acetylcholine

Acetylcholine (ACh) is another widely used neurotransmitter, released in all autonomic nerve fibers that leave the central nervous system and in all postganglionic parasympathetic fibers (38). In arteries, ACh release causes endothelium-dependent vasodilation (38).

Endothelin

Endothelins are 21-amino acid peptides that mediate the vascular tone. They have a distinctive “shepherd’s crook” structure mediated by two internal disulfide bonds. The three isoforms,

endothelin-1, endothelin-2, and endothelin-3 (ET-1, ET-2 and ET-3) are differently expressed in different organs. The two primary endothelin receptors are ET_A and ET_B, both of which are G protein coupled (38). ET_A receptors are expressed in many human tissues, including vascular smooth muscle, heart, lung, and kidney, but not in the endothelium (38). Stimulation of ET_A causes vasoconstriction through inositol triphosphate-mediated calcium release (38). ET_B receptors are mainly expressed in the brain, with moderate expression in the aorta, heart, lung, kidney, and adrenals (38). It is expressed in the endothelium, where it causes vasodilation by stimulating NO and PGI₂ production. However, ET_B receptors are also present in vascular smooth muscle, where they mediate vasoconstriction, just like the ET_A receptors (38).

First, among the endothelin isoforms, ET-1 primarily activates ET_A receptors but also has some affinity for ET_B. It is widely distributed in endothelial cells and other tissues (38). In contrast, ET-3 is predominantly found in the brain, lung, intestine, and adrenal gland, with a preference for ET_B receptors (38). Second, sarafotoxins, a group of snake venom toxins, exhibit structural and functional similarity to endothelins. Sarafotoxin 6b acts as a nonselective ET agonist (9), while sarafotoxin 6c selectively targets ET_B receptors (38). Finally, several pharmacological agents modulate endothelin receptor activity. BQ3020 and Ala^{1,3,11,15}-ET-1 are selective ET_B receptor agonists (9), whereas BQ123 is a cyclic pentapeptide that functions as a selective ET_A receptor antagonist (38).

Prostanoids

Prostaglandin F-2 α (PGF_{2 α}) is a prostanoid and acts on prostaglandin F (FP) receptors in smooth muscle cells (primarily in the uterine), producing contraction (38).

Nitrates

Nitrates release nitric oxide (NO), which relaxes smooth muscle, with the strongest effect occurring in veins. NO stimulates the formation of cGMP which activates protein kinase G. This affects the myosin light chains and calcium regulation, causing decreased levels of intracellular calcium and thus relaxation. Notably, this pathway is endothelium-independent (38).

Studies included in this review used several nitrates. First, sodium nitroprusside (SNP) is an inorganic nitrate that functions as an NO donor (38). Second, nitroglycerin (NTG) is an organic nitrate that is rapidly absorbed through the oral mucosa when administered as a sublingual spray, producing a fast but short-lived effect (38). Finally, isosorbide dinitrate is another organic nitrate that is converted into NO (38).

Calcium antagonists

Calcium antagonists block the entry of Ca^{2+} into the cells through calcium channels. Therapeutically, the most important type acts on the L-type channels. This type of drugs binds to the α_1 subunit of these calcium channels to prevent its opening, but different classes (phenylalkylamines, dihydropyridines and benzothiazepines) bind at different sites. Calcium channel antagonists mainly affect the heart and smooth muscle. The vasodilatory effect is believed to be mainly on muscular arteries (38).

Two different calcium antagonists are described in this review. First, nifedipine is a dihydropyridine type of calcium antagonist. It acts on the L-type calcium channels, mainly from smooth muscle cells, causing dilation. More specifically, it binds selectively to the channels in mode 0, when it does not open in response to depolarization (38). Second, diltiazem, a benzothiazepine type of calcium antagonist, acts on the L-type calcium channels. It exerts effect on both the heart and smooth muscle cells (38).

Endothelium-derived hyperpolarization factors

Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) is an endothelium-derived hyperpolarization factor (EDHF) and is an essential component of the signal transduction pathway for vasodilation (38).

Exercise

During exercise, the cardiovascular system needs to accommodate for the increased oxygen demand of the body. To achieve this, sympathetic activity rises, leading to an elevated cardiac output and redistribution of blood flow. Autoregulation results in local vasodilation in high-demanding muscles, whereas vasoconstriction takes place in the digestive system and large veins to redistribute the blood flow and increase the effective circulating blood volume (39).

Non-bleeding fluid deficiency

Fluid deficiency during hemorrhage, blood donation or dialysis causes a sympathetic response to maintain enough blood flow to the vital organs. A similar effect can be obtained by non-bleeding fluid deficiency. Scuba divers, for example, lose a considerable amount of fluid per dive, mainly due to immersion-related autonomic responses, such as increased diuresis, sweating and humidification of dry breathing gasses. This can serve as a controlled case for the effect of fluid deficiency on the hemodynamic system.

Cold pressor test

The cold pressor test (CPT) is used to stimulate the sympathetic nervous system by immersing a hand in ice-cold water. The vascular response varies depending on the blood vessels involved. In healthy individuals, CPT typically induces vasodilation in peripheral and coronary arteries. However,

in individuals with impaired vascular health, this response may be diminished or even result in vasoconstriction (40, 41).

Tilting

The tilt test is used to evaluate the response of the autonomic nervous system to change in posture. In the first 3 minutes after upright tilt a portion of the blood volume displaces to the splanchnic circulation and lower limbs. This results in a decrease of blood pressure at the baroreceptors, triggering the sympathetic nervous system (42).

Lower body negative pressure

Applying negative pressure on the lower body, also results in a blood shift towards the lower body. The concomitant hypovolemia in the central part of the body activates the baroreflex (43).

Smoking

Tobacco smoking and even passive smoking are known to have several unfavorable effects on the cardiovascular system. This includes endothelial dysfunction, atherosclerosis and oxidative stress. Moreover, smoking is thought to activate the sympathetic system (44).

Cocaine

Cocaine is a local anesthetic and is mostly used as a recreational drug. At lower doses, cocaine induces euphoria, while at higher doses, it stimulates the central nervous system by blocking the reuptake of amines. Additionally, it inhibits noradrenaline reuptake, which amplifies sympathetic activity, resulting in tachycardia and vasoconstriction (38).

Anesthetics

Propofol is used for the induction and maintenance of general anesthesia(38). It has a fast onset and is short acting (38). Nitrous oxide (N₂O) is a frequently used adjunct to propofol anesthesia (36), which reduces the need of propofol. N₂O acts rapidly on the NMDA receptors and already has analgesic properties on concentrations too low to cause unconsciousness (38). Nitrous oxide alone increases the sympathetic signals and increases the heart rate and maintains blood pressure (38).

Meal consumption

After consuming a meal, the splanchnic circulation vasodilates. This vasodilation causes a blood flow redistribution in which the flow in the splanchnic circulation can be increased up to eight times. The splanchnic blood flow remains elevated for 2 to 4 hours after a meal (39).